

THE PLOT AND VERSIONS OF “BAKHROM AND GULANDOM” IN SAYQALIY’S WORKS

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Abstract. This article examines the plot of the epic “*Bakhrom and Gulandom*” by Sobir Sayqaliy, an 18th-century Uzbek poet, as well as its various versions in Uzbek literature.

Keywords: *uzbek literature, Sobir Sayqaliy, Bakhrom and Gulandom, epic, plot, Bakhrom Gur, heroic-adventure, Ferdowsi, Nizami, Khusrau Dehlavi, Navoi.*

The Relationship Between the Plot of *Bakhrom Gur* and the Plot of *Bakhrom va Gulandom*.

In Uzbek literature, alongside the plot of *Bakhrom Gur*, which is related to Bakhrom and a concubine (in *Ferdowsi* it’s *Bakhrom and Ozoda*, in *Nizami* it’s *Bakhrom and Fitna*, in *Khusraw Dehlavi* and *Navoi* it’s *Bakhrom and Dilorom*), the plot of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* also gained widespread popularity. The plot of *Bakhrom and Kanizak* was developed in the *Khamsa* works and became an integral part of classical literature, later circulating among the people. Meanwhile, *Bakhrom and Gulandom* initially gained fame in oral folk traditions, then transitioned into written literature and later returned to folklore.

In Uzbek literature, versions of the plot of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* are more often found in the folk variants of the story. Although this plot originally appeared in the folklore of Eastern nations, it was first introduced into written literature through Sobir Sayqali’s epic *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, which entered Uzbek literature in the 13th century.

In the first chapter of the book, as previously mentioned, there is a significant distinction between the plot of *Bakhrom Gur* in *Khamsa* and the plot of *Bakhrom and Gulandom*. Although both plots involve the character Bakhrom, the plot of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* is not a direct continuation of the story *Bakhrom Gur*. The differences between these two plots are more pronounced than their similarities. The main distinction lies in the fact that the plot of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* originated in folk oral traditions and reflects many folkloric characteristics.

While the emergence of the plot of *Bakhrom Gur* is influenced by both historical events and folkloric elements, it has been adapted over the centuries by great figures, refined to meet the demands of written literature, and aligned with the conventions of classical Eastern epic poetry. This is especially evident in the works of Navoi, who took this genre to unparalleled heights.

The story of *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, known in popular tales, shares structural similarities not only in certain elements or episodes but also in its overall composition with folk tales, novels, and epics that circulated in the Near and Middle East. It features fairy-tale-like adventures, a romantic atmosphere, the participation of supernatural forces (mythical elements), heroes with boundless power and potential, and a storyline where the forces of good always prevail, often with ease and simplicity. These features, as well as the plot’s alignment with the character’s motives and actions, align it with the genre of popular literature—romantic and heroic-adventure tales—widely spread among the people.

Although the plot of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* shares similarities with folk literature, it is also clearly influenced by classical literary traditions. This blending of oral folklore with written

literature is particularly evident in Sobir Sayqali's epic, where the influences of both traditions coexist and interact. This connection between oral and written traditions is a key feature, and it reflects the broader relationship between oral folk storytelling and the written literary form.

Now, let's examine the connections and differences between the plot of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* and the plot of *Bakhrom Gur*. For this, we need to first present the core events that serve as the foundation for all the works associated with *Bakhrom and Gulandom*. (The version of the events we provide here is of a general nature; each version of the story has undergone variations, and these differences will be discussed during the analysis of each work.)

Core Plot of Bakhrom and Gulandom:

The plot begins with a wise and just king in Rum, who, despite his great wealth, has no children. After many years, the king is finally blessed with a son, whom he names Bakhrom. The boy is raised by a wet nurse and later educated in a school, mastering various arts and sciences by the age of 16. He becomes a powerful warrior and expert hunter. The king, overjoyed at the birth of his son, crowns him, gives him a portion of the army, and advises him to rule with justice, compassion, and wisdom.

Bakhrom accepts his father's advice and asks for permission to go hunting. On his first hunting trip, he kills a lion and is praised for his bravery. The next day, while hunting a deer, he becomes separated from his army. Lost, Bakhrom climbs a mountain and encounters an old man's hut. Inside, the old man shows him a picture of a beautiful young woman — Gulandom, the daughter of the Roman king.

Bakhrom falls in love with the portrait and asks the old man for directions to her homeland. He sets out on his journey and soon encounters a land of demons. He battles and defeats three demons: Sayfur, Shammos, and Qammos. When Bakhrom is about to kill them, the demons' sister, Sarvos, pleads for mercy, and Bakhrom spares their lives. The demons, now grateful, become his friends and host him in their home, where they hold a feast. Bakhrom then kills the Aqrab demon in a cave at Sayfur's request, freeing Sayfur's wife, Rukhafzon, and claiming a large treasure.

After parting from the demons, Bakhrom continues his quest for Gulandom. During a sea voyage, a shark (nahang) attacks their ship, further testing Bakhrom's strength and bravery.

This plot, with its adventures, supernatural encounters, and heroic actions, shares many elements with romantic and heroic folk tales. These elements include the protagonist's extraordinary strength and abilities, the presence of mythical creatures, and the frequent intervention of divine or supernatural forces to ensure the protagonist's success. Despite its roots in folk tradition, the plot of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* also demonstrates the marks of classical literature, particularly in how it structures and refines the traditional themes of adventure, love, and heroism.

In this way, Sobir Sayqali's *Bakhrom and Gulandom* illustrates the dynamic interplay between oral folklore and written literary forms, highlighting both the continuity of folkloric elements and their transformation into a more sophisticated literary expression.

The narrative of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* continues with dramatic events that deepen the emotional complexity of the story and the interaction between the two main characters, Bakhrom and Gulandom.

As the plot unfolds, the sea voyage and the encounter with the shark (nahang) test Bakhrom's courage and skill. After the fight with the shark, Bakhrom reaches the city of Rum and learns that Bekhzod of Bulgar has laid siege to the city, attempting to forcefully take Gulandom.

Bakhrom, determined to save her, disguises himself in the clothes of a palace servant and surveys the enemy troops. He then changes back into his royal attire and, with the help of his allies, launches a surprise attack on Bekhzod's forces. The battle results in a great victory, with Bekhzod's head placed on a spear at the city gate as a symbol of his defeat and wickedness.

In a symbolic act of justice, Bakhrom leaves a letter for the people of Rum, stating that anyone who desires Bekhzod's blood should seek it from him, as Bakhrom has avenged the wrongs done to Gulandom. After this, Bakhrom returns to his position, taking his place at the entrance of Gulandom's palace, where he waits for her.

The people of Rum are astonished by the events, and the king's minister speculates that Bakhrom's love for Gulandom must be celestial, as if the god of the thunder (chaqmoq xudosi) had descended to earth to punish Bekhzod's evil. This mystical explanation is accepted, and the letter from the slain Bekhzod is stored in the royal treasury.

Meanwhile, Bakhrom continues to observe Gulandom from a distance, captivated by her beauty. On one occasion, while the palace is holding its usual tradition of displaying Gulandom's beauty to the people, Bakhrom is so struck by her that he loses his senses. When he recovers, he finds that it is already late, and the crowd has dispersed. Undeterred, he climbs to the roof of the palace and gazes through a hole in the window to watch her throughout the night.

On the day of a ritual where Gulandom sends her maids outside to collect gifts from the people, Bakhrom takes the opportunity to send her a valuable ring. Upon receiving the ring, Gulandom realizes that the young man is none other than the prince of Rum, and her feelings begin to change. She gives him special attention the next time the ritual takes place, and their eyes meet, igniting a mutual love between them.

Gulandom, moved by the depth of Bakhrom's feelings, sends her servant, Davlat, to inquire about him. Bakhrom, in turn, reveals his love for her through a letter, and their communication through love letters begins. These letters form a significant part of the epic, with ten letters exchanged between the two characters. The first set of letters expresses Bakhrom's deep sorrow and longing, while Gulandom initially rejects him, questioning his identity and worth. As the exchange continues, Bakhrom reveals his true identity as a prince, and Gulandom, now touched by his sincerity, advises him to remain patient and not to publicize their love too hastily.

In time, Bakhrom's love and patience win over Gulandom, and they both fall in love with each other. This marks the conclusion of the first part of the epic, which is centered around their emotional journey and the development of their deep affection.

This section of the narrative underscores themes of love, fate, and personal transformation, with Bakhrom's sincere devotion ultimately winning Gulandom's heart. The poetic exchanges between the lovers, expressed through letters and their emotional dialogues, serve as the foundation for the romantic and heroic qualities that define this epic. The symbolism of the letters as a form of communication also highlights the cultural importance of written expression in the development of relationships in classical literature.

The second part of the narrative can be described as the resolution and conclusion of the plot. In this section, several important events unfold that bring closure to the story.

First, Bakhrom's father, the king, sends out people in search of his son after hearing nothing from him for a long time. The search leads to the discovery of Bakhrom's whereabouts when a hermit named Ravshanzamir, who had shown Bakhrom the portrait of Gulandom, informs the king of his son's location. Meanwhile, the Rum emperor's diplomats, led by the vizier Dastur, travel to

the country of Chin, where they find Bakhrom after reading the letter that was left at the city gate, signaling Bakhrom's victorious campaign over Bekhzod.

In a celebratory feast, Bakhrom invites Sayfur's army of spirits and demons to show them his victory over Bekhzod's forces. During the event, he recounts how he defeated Bekhzod's troops. However, just as the celebrations continue, Navshod arrives with his army, seeking revenge for Bekhzod. Bakhrom, with the help of the armies of the Chin king and Sayfur, enters battle once again and defeats Navshod.

After the military conflicts are resolved, the narrative shifts to the ceremonial processes of betrothal and marriage. Gulandom is promised to Bakhrom, and Sayfur's sister, Sarvoso, is betrothed to Fagfur. Following the wedding, Bakhrom bids farewell to the king of Chin and sets out on his journey back to Rum.

The story concludes with the traditional optimistic sentence, "May the tale, as well as its meaning and purpose, be fulfilled," marking the end of this epic narrative. The resolution ties up the loose ends of the story, bringing about the union of Bakhrom and Gulandom, and the fulfillment of the quest and the protagonist's desires.

The detailed exposition of the plot in this section aims to provide a clearer understanding of the similarities and differences between the plot of "Bakhrom and Gulandom" and the plot of "Bakhrom Gur". Additionally, the goal is to study the general and specific aspects of these Uzbek epic narratives, avoiding unnecessary repetition in the process.

Now, let's compare the two types of plots, from both written and oral literature, focusing on their similarities.

The exposition of the plot "Bakhrom and Gulandom", particularly its initial episodes, is quite similar to the events depicted in the works of Firdausi, Nizami, Khosrow Dehlavi, and Navoi. For instance, Bakhrom being the only child in the family, born after many prayers and sacrifices, and growing up to be wise and courageous, is a theme that is present in both *Shakhnameh* and *Khaft Paykar*. These events are briefly referenced in *Khasht Bekhisht* and *Sab'a-i Sayyor*. However, in *Shakhnameh* and *Khaft Paykar*, much more attention is paid to Bakhrom's upbringing and his skills in hunting, while in *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, these events are mentioned much more briefly. If we disregard the depiction of the lion hunt, the exposition in *Bakhrom and Gulandom* closely resembles that in the works of Khosrow Dehlavi and Navoi. Yet, the lion-hunting episode connects the plot to the works of Nizami and Firdausi as well. The way Bakhrom deals with the lion in this episode is reminiscent of the depiction in *Shakhnameh* and *Khaft Paykar* (for instance, in *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, like in those works, the prince grabs the lion by its hind legs and spins it around to strike it dead).

As the exposition progresses, Bakhrom's pursuit of a deer and his accidental discovery of Gulandom's portrait is closer to the narratives in Navoi and Khosrow Dehlavi than to Firdausi and Nizami. While in Nizami's *Khaft Paykar*, Bakhrom falls in love with the portraits of the princesses in the seven pavilions, he does not fall in love with any particular portrait with the intention of meeting the woman behind it. Nizami uses the portraits to symbolically represent the seven pavilions and the seven princesses, and their future destiny with Bakhrom. In *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, however, the portrait directly serves as a plot device, advancing the narrative and acting as a key element of the storyline.

In *Sab'a-i Sayyor*, the portrait of Dilorom shown to Bakhrom by Moniy serves a similar purpose as a plot device, marking a pivotal moment in the story. Similarly, the sequence of events

following Bakhrom's pursuit of the deer, where he accidentally enters a cave and sees Gulandom's portrait, aligns with themes found in the closing episodes of *Khamsa* works. The scene where Bakhrom follows the deer into a cave is drawn from the plot of *Bakhrom Gur*.

From this point onward, the events in the narrative of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* diverge significantly from the plot of *Bakhrom Gur*.

In *Shakhsnameh*, the episode where Bakhrom changes his appearance and travels to India as an envoy, demonstrating heroism and marrying the king's daughter, is similar in general direction to the part of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* where Bakhrom, not revealing his identity, demonstrates bravery and eventually becomes close to the princess. However, the similarities end there. The central events of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* (battles with devils, defeating them, fighting at sea, and the massacre in China for the sake of the beloved) are much more aligned with other works from the *Khamsa* collection rather than the plot of *Bakhrom Gur*. For example, in *Farkhod and Shirin*, Farkhod's status as the only child, his courageous and wise upbringing, his father's call for a council to hand over the throne, Farkhod falling in love with Shirin's portrait, and his arduous journey to Armenia (including the sea disaster), and the conflict with Khosrow who forces Shirin's hand (similar to how Bekhzod leads an army to capture Gulandom) all resemble the adventures of Bakhrom in *Bakhrom and Gulandom*. However, *Farkhod and Shirin* is a work with a particular ideological-aesthetic aim and ends in tragedy, while in *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, Bakhrom ultimately succeeds in achieving his goal and is united with his beloved.

Thus, while there are some narrative similarities between *Bakhrom and Gulandom* and *Bakhrom Gur*, particularly in terms of minor plot elements, the core episodes are distinct. The development, climax, resolution, and conclusion of the story differ in terms of content, theme, and narrative style, demonstrating that *Bakhrom and Gulandom* is an independent story with a new form. The shift in plot also leads to differences in the story's ideological content, symbolism, and character development.

In terms of theme, the plot of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* is distinct from the plot of *Bakhrom Gur*. In the latter, the central themes in the stories are: in *Shakhsnameh*, heroism and justice (with kingship as a secondary concern); in *Khafth Paykar*, governance and love (with heroism as secondary); in *Khasht Behisht*, love and materialism (with heroism almost absent); and in *Sab'a-i Sayyor*, love and kingship (with no heroism at all). In contrast, the main theme of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* is love. Although heroism plays a significant role, it is not the central theme; it is subordinated to the theme of love. However, the way this theme is artistically resolved and expressed differs significantly.

In the *Khamsa* works, Bakhrom in the epic *Bakhrom Gur* is portrayed as a powerful, arrogant king of seven climates, a man who prides himself excessively on his power and abilities. He desires total obedience from everyone and aims to spend his life in pleasure and indulgence. He falls in love with a beautiful concubine but is not a true lover. Although Bakhrom changes and loves Dilorom sincerely by the end of Navoiy's work, he remains on his own path and tragically dies in a hunting accident. In these works, the contrast between love and kingship is well-explored, depicting Bakhrom's internal conflict between his ambitions and his emotions. In *Bakhrom Gur*, Dilorom is a symbol of love but also objectified as a beautiful being, not treated as an equal human.

In comparison, the character of Bakhrom in *Bakhrom and Gulandom* is less focused on pride and more on the theme of love, marking a shift in both narrative structure and character dynamics. The central conflict is not between kingship and love but rather Bakhrom's journey of

love, with heroism acting as a tool in this pursuit. This makes the story's thematic core distinctly different from the epic *Bakhrom Gur*.

In *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, Bakhrom is portrayed as a brave, heroic lover who eases the burdens of others, extending a helping hand in difficult times. Despite being a prince, and even though he is a hero who has defeated invaders in Gulandom's homeland, he does not act arrogantly before his beloved. He does not try to forcibly win her love (unlike Bakhrom Gur, who uses wealth and power to bring Dilorom to him). Instead, Bakhrom patiently expresses his love and loyalty through passionate letters, ultimately winning the princess's heart. As a result, their love emerges from mutual consent and equality, with Bakhrom earning the love through his valor and heroic deeds. His quest is solely to win the heart of his beloved, and all his actions are directed towards this goal.

Gulandom is intelligent, noble, and shrewd. She loves Bakhrom not because of his royal status, but because of his courage, heroism, and steadfast devotion in love. She exercises her own will in choosing a partner, and her father's judgment does not override her own feelings. The characters in *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, including Bakhrom's allies, act independently and are not merely subjects obeying his will as in *Sab 'a-i Sayyor*. Even when they assist Bakhrom, they do so out of friendship and brotherhood, not because they are bound to execute his orders (e.g., Sayfur and others). Bakhrom is depicted as a noble and compassionate prince, striving for justice, kindness, and peace.

Another notable aspect of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* is that, unlike the tragic endings typical in *Khamsa*, the story concludes on an optimistic note. In contrast, the Bakhrom of *Khamsa*, who takes on the title *Gur*, foreshadows his tragic, mysterious demise. This contrast suggests that although the story *Bakhrom and Gulandom* is influenced by classical literary traditions, it has its own distinct narrative path. While there are minor thematic and structural links to the epic *Bakhrom Gur*, the core of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* is different, with a narrative that emphasizes positive qualities like love, heroism, and cooperation rather than the tragic, ambiguous nature of the earlier works.

The plot of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* belongs to a different development trajectory than the stories *Bakhrom Gur*. As a folk narrative, it incorporates elements of folklore, with fantastical elements, such as the participation of supernatural forces and a fairy-tale-like structure. This is evident in the nature of the characters and their actions, which are more aligned with folk epics than courtly narratives.

Research by R. Aliyev and A. A. Semenov suggests that the story *Bakhrom and Gulandom* differs significantly from the stories *Bakhrom Gur*, regarding its subject matter and character development. They highlight Bakhrom's depiction in *Bakhrom and Gulandom* as an "ideal prince", free from negative traits. According to them, Bakhrom in this version is a heroic figure, removed from the flaws present in the earlier Bakhrom. The narrative, while rooted in the classical tradition, presents a more optimistic, idealized hero who embodies the virtues of courage, justice, and love.

Overall, *Bakhrom and Gulandom* is a folk epic that reflects the folk mentality, focusing on adventure, the triumph of the hero, and the achievement of the hero's goals rather than a stark battle between opposing forces. The nature of the heroism and the plot structure in this work is what distinguishes it from the *Khamsa* epics, making it an independent and unique tale.

In *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, the central conflict or "contradiction" does not arise from a sharp opposition of forces but rather from Bakhrom's love for Gulandom and the difficulties he

faces in winning her heart. Although Bakhrom falls in love with Gulandom after seeing her portrait (the climax of the story), the primary questions that occupy his mind are how to win her over, whether she loves him, and what actions he must take to gain her affection. All the events that unfold throughout the story are focused on Bakhrom's pursuit of his goal—winning Gulandom's love. The climax of the tale comes when Bakhrom finally receives a letter from Gulandom, and at this moment, he earns her love. This is the moment when Bakhrom discovers the path to achieving his aim.

The composition of the narrative and the arrangement of events are perfectly suited to the story's progression. Bakhrom's character does not undergo a radical transformation but rather, his qualities are revealed gradually throughout the story. In contrast to dynamic characters in stories of sharp conflict, the characters in *Bakhrom and Gulandom* are more fully formed from the outset. This type of narrative, in which the character's qualities unfold rather than develop in opposition to a contrasting force, is typical of adventure stories where the hero's actions and victories are the main focus.

Thus, *Bakhrom and Gulandom* reflects the characteristics of a folk epic. It shares key elements with "typical folk epics", such as the presence of "chivalric romance", the heroic dedication of the protagonist, and the element of fantastical adventure. These traits distinguish the work from more psychological, written literature. In Uzbek literature, several works exist under the name *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, but the relationship between them, as well as their specific features, has not been fully explored. The origins of the shared narrative and the sources of these stories have not been thoroughly investigated.

R. Aliyev was one of the first to address this topic and pointed out that the events in *Bakhrom and Gulandom* by Sobir Sayqaliy are similar to the Persian prose story *Shakhzoda Bakhrom va Malikai Gulandom* and to the version by Fozil Yuldosh ugli. However, Aliyev does not delve into the origins of these stories or fully explore the differences between them.

Orientalist scholar K.G. Korogli, in his article, mentions that Sayqali's epic might have been based on a widely circulated Persian prose story, which had been lithographed several times. Korogli notes the similarities between the two storylines and also identifies elements that are characteristic of Sayqaliy's style. However, like Aliyev, Korogli does not investigate the origin of the Persian prose story.

Literary scholar A.A. Gvakharyan, in his article on the Persian and Georgian versions of *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, provides information about a Persian poetic version of the epic, authored by Mukhammad Amin. He points out that the manuscript versions of this epic are preserved in Dushanbe and Tbilisi archives. Gvakharyan also refers to the works of Iranian scholar Mukhammad Ja'far Makhjub, who suggests that the story *Bakhrom and Gulandom* is a reworked version of Nizami's *Khaf Paykar*.

This scholarly work demonstrates the complex origins and interrelations of various versions of the narrative *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, highlighting both the folk and classical elements in the story's development across cultures.

In his research on the Kurdish version of *Bakhrom and Gulandom*, Qodir Fattohiy Qozi analyzes and compares the Kurdish text with the Persian version. While he does not provide specific information about the origins or the period of the work's creation, he references the well-known scholar Said Nafisiy, who stated: "Since the 10th century, several important books have reached us, including *Iskandarnama* ("The Tale of Rum"), *Khamseh Jangnomas*, *The Forty*

Parrots, The Four Dervishes, Bakhrom and Gulandom, Khatami Toy, The Tale of Amir Arslon, and other minor books". Nafisiy emphasizes that *Bakhrom and Gulandom* originates from folklore and is similar to other epic tales like *Amir Arslon*. He also notes that this tale bears similarities to the *Vis Ramin* story (by Fakhriddin Gurgoni, 11th century), though it has undergone changes in later centuries.

According to Nafisiy and Qozi, the origins of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* date back to the 10th–11th centuries, and like other folklore, it was born from the imagination of the people. This idea is also supported by the introduction to the Persian version, which mentions a collection of tales written in the 13th century. It should also be noted that some folklore works have been influenced by written literature, and *Bakhrom and Gulandom* is one of them. This distinguishes it from works like *The Four Dervishes* and *Amir Arslon*.

Based on the research, it is clear that *Bakhrom and Gulandom* originated in Persia and spread widely among Near Eastern cultures (including Uzbek, Georgian, Kurdish, etc.). However, the versions differ across regions. For example, the Kurdish version significantly deviates from the Persian and Uzbek versions, with new symbols, events, and a different analysis of the plot. There are also various Uzbek versions of *Bakhrom and Gulandom*. To date, three main Uzbek versions were known (created by Sayqali, Fozil Yuldosh ugli, and a prose translation by Sidqiy Khondayliq), but further research has revealed another Uzbek version in the manuscript collection of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. This version, written in a mixed prose-verse style, closely resembles Fozil Yuldosh ugli's version and likely dates back to the late 19th century.

Furthermore, N.P. Ostroumov's *Narodnye skazki sartov* mentions *Shakhzoda Bakhrom* (Prince Bakhrom) as a widely spread folk tale, which is considered an oral variant of *Shakhzoda Bakhrom va Malikai Gulandom*.

The versions of *Bakhrom and Gulandom* in Uzbek literature share many common features in terms of plot development and character participation. However, there are notable differences in their thematic depth, character development, the portrayal of symbols, literary techniques, and descriptive styles. These differences contribute to the unique aesthetic value and impact of each version, making them worthy of individual analysis.

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